

THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF RURAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract— Entrepreneurship is the process of creating new enterprise, bearing any of its risk with the view of making profit. Entrepreneurship is an important / engine for the growth of economy. Rural entrepreneurship refers to the entrepreneurship rising at village level which can occur in a variety of areas such as business, agriculture, industry as well as acts as a useful factor for economic development. Rural entrepreneurship plays an imperative role in the overall development of the country's economy. The development of rural entrepreneurship aids the advancement of self employment, resulting in wider distribution of economic as well as industrial activities and helps in the maximum utilization of locally available raw materials and labour. It plays a vital role in the development of Indian Economy as majority of its population belongs to rural area. Promoting rural entrepreneurship is essential for removal or reduction of poverty and helping in Economic growth of our Country. This paper aims at identifying the opportunities available for rural entrepreneurs in Odisha and what strategies should be implemented to create more rural entrepreneur for the development of rural area in order to achieve a balanced regional development. The primary data has been collected from selected district in the state of Odisha. The paper also comprises of secondary data collected from information from different websites.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, rural entrepreneurs, economy, economic growth, balanced regional development.

INTRODUCTION

An entrepreneur is one who owns and operates an enterprise, who is willing to take risks by exploiting new market opportunities by bringing up new production factors; for instance making use of innovative methods of production, introducing fresh products into new markets and finding new sources of supply to the ultimate consumers. Entrepreneurship is an important factor for accelerating overall rural development.

Rural entrepreneurship can be defined as entrepreneurship budding at rural level that can take place in various forms of ventures such as business, agriculture and manufacturing unit and act as a crucial factor for the economic growth of the region. Indian rural sector is no longer archaic and isolated. Therefore, introduction of entrepreneurship in rural areas

could help in alleviating the problems of poverty, unemployment, and economic disparity, poor utilization of rural capacity, low standard of living and backwardness of Indian economy. Rural industrialization can be considered as an effective means of escalating the growth of rural areas. Government of India has been constantly extending support for the promotion and growth of rural entrepreneurship.

About 83.31% of population of Odisha state lives in rural area. So rural entrepreneurship development can help in tackling the problems by providing occupation to the rural youths. The need is to plant other option in the minds of rural youth. Entrepreneurship could be the best option. If planted and nurtured in the minds of rural women and youth, It could result is revolutionizing the Indian economy

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study made by **Babu (2012), Singh J.(2013), Pal(2013), Ghosh(2013)** reveals that entrepreneurs taking to rural entrepreneurship should not only set-up enterprises in rural areas but should also use rural produce as raw material and employ rural people in their production process.

Venkateswarlu & Ravindra (2015) found that introduction of rural entrepreneurship is the response towards removal of rural poverty in India and in order to make entrepreneurship development more effective there is a need to change the thinking. Entrepreneurship development should be an integral part of school education.

Ravikumar B. M. (2015) states that due to lack of education, majority of rural people are unaware of technological development, marketing etc. Most of the rural entrepreneurs face unusual troubles like fear of risk, lack of training, illiteracy, and experience, limited purchasing power and competition from urban entrepreneurs. Promotion of rural entrepreneurship is a answer to develop rural areas and backward towns.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The main objective of the paper is to study the socio-economic characteristics of rural entrepreneurs in Jagatsinghpur District of Odisha. The detailed objectives to the study are as follows:

1. To study the facilities available for rural entrepreneurs in Odisha.
2. To study the problems related to rural entrepreneurship in Odisha.
3. To enquire into the socio-economic background of rural entrepreneurs in the above mentioned district.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀-Socio-economic factors are not encouraging towards the growth of rural entrepreneurship

METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology adopted which includes sampling technique, collection of data and analysis.

Size of sample was determined by applying Krejcie and Morgan's formula of "Determining Sample Size for Research Activities" from a total population (N=500).

The formula is $S = \frac{X^2 NP (1 - P)}{d^2 (N - 1) + X^2 P (1 - P)}$

S = required sample size.

X^2 = Chi Square

N = the population size.

P = the population proportion (assumed to be 0.50 level since this would provide the maximum Sample size).

d = the degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion (0.05 level).

Accordingly the number of sample size or respondents was found to be 288. These 288 samples were drawn considering Jagatsinghpur district as a whole population by the simple random sampling method. Primary Data has been collected through interview after considering all the relevant aspects required. The secondary data were collected from published, unpublished reports, handbooks etc

Simple percentage analysis has been applied to find out the demographic profile of rural entrepreneurs. Chi-square test with cross tab technique by SPSS has been used for testing hypothesis.

Facilities available for Rural Entrepreneurs

1. Low Establishment and Production Cost: In comparison to the urban areas, establishment cost for rural entrepreneurship is very low. Huge infrastructures and buildings are also not required to set up business in a rural area.

2. **Competitive advantages of labor:** 83.31% of the population of Odisha are living in rural areas and Majority of them are depending on agriculture. Rural entrepreneurs have the competitive advantage over acquiring unskilled and semi-skilled labor as agriculture work is not available throughout the year.
3. **Availability of raw materials:** Rural entrepreneurs are mostly dependent on the farm based products for raw materials, which are easily available through-out the year in rural area hence there is no transportation cost and flotation cost involved.
4. **Employment generation for rural youth:** Development of rural entrepreneurship will help in generating employment opportunities for rural youth and help in reduction in migration of the people from rural to urban to a maximum extent.
5. **Government policies and subsidies:** The government is continuously keeping track and introducing the new policies for encouraging the rural entrepreneurship. The government has also announced huge subsidies for promoting the rural entrepreneurship.

Some important and popular Govt. schemes are discussed below:

1. **Pradhan Mantri Rojgar Protsahan Yojana (PMRPY)**
This Scheme came into force in Aug, 2016 to stimulate employers for generation of new employment opportunities, where Government of India will be paying the full employer's contribution towards EPF & EPS both w.e.f 01.04.2018 for the new employment.
2. **Rajiv Gandhi Udyami Mitra Yojana (RGUMY)**
This scheme was introduced in 2008 to provide encouragement and assistance to the potential 1st generation entrepreneurs through 'Udyami Mitras', in dealing with establishment and management of the new enterprise. To provide guidance, support, and aid to entrepreneurs through an 'Udyami Helpline' (a Call Centre for MSMEs) to guide them about different promotional schemes, procedural formalities required for setting up and running of the enterprise and help them in accessing Bank credit etc.
3. **Credit Guarantee Scheme for Micro and Small Enterprises (CGTMSE)**
On 30th Aug, 2000 the MSME Ministry and Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI) jointly established a Trust called Credit Guarantee Fund Trust for Micro and Small Enterprises in order to implement Credit Guarantee Scheme for Micro and Small Enterprises. The scheme provides collateral-free loan up to a limit of Rs 100 lakh for individual MSMEs on payment of a guarantee fee to the bank by the MSME.

PROBLEMS FACED BY RURAL ENTREPRENEURS

➤ **FINANCIAL PROBLEMS**

1. SCARCITY OF FUNDS Due to absence of tangible security most of the rural entrepreneurs fail to arrange funds and credit in the market. This in turn disappoints the rural entrepreneurs. Lack of availability of finance to rural entrepreneurs is one of the major problems which rural entrepreneur is facing these days.

2. LACK OF INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITIES

Rural areas face a lot of problems related to electricity, roads, road transportation system which hampers the smooth functioning of rural industries. This restricts the growth of rural entrepreneurs in spite of the efforts by government due to lack of proper infrastructural facilities.

3. THREAT ELEMENT Due to lack of financial and external support the rural entrepreneurs have less threat bearing capacity.

➤ **MARKETING PROBLEMS**

1. CUTTHROAT COMPETITION Rural entrepreneurs face cut throat competition from large organizations and urban entrepreneurs. The rural entrepreneur are not collective in their approach for marketing their products because they are to widely scattered and uneducated.

2. MIDDLEMEN Rural entrepreneurs are mostly exploited by the middlemen. The middlemen pocket large amount of profit as the rural entrepreneurs are highly dependent on them for marketing of their products.

➤ **MANAGEMENT PROBLEMS**

1. LEGAL FORMALITIES Due to lack of awareness and proper education Rural entrepreneurs find it extremely difficult in complying with various legal formalities for obtaining government’s approval and licenses for carrying out various business activities.

2. PROCUREMENT OF RAW MATERIALS

Procurement of raw materials gets really tough for rural entrepreneur. Rural industries tend to be smaller so the entrepreneurs in rural areas procure raw materials at a very higher rate from the middlemen. So they may end up with poor quality raw materials and also face the problem of storage and warehousing.

3. LACK OF TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE Due to Lack of proper training facilities rural Indian people don’t have well-built technical knowledge which restrains these people to employ latest technology.

4. POOR QUALITY OF PRODUCTS Lack of availability of standard tools and equipment and poor quality of raw materials results in production of inferior quality products, which hinders the growth of rural entrepreneurship.

➤ **HUMAN RESOURCES PROBLEMS**

1. UNSKILLED WORKERS Due to lack of proper education and training facilities most of the rural workers are unskilled; hence most of the entrepreneurs of rural areas are unable to find workers who are highly skilled.

2. PESSIMISTIC ATTITUDE The rural environment doesn’t prove to be conducive, in order to encourage rural people to take up entrepreneurship as their career; hence the youth as well as the literate mostly tend to migrate. It is sometime difficult for an entrepreneur to impart rural employees with continuous motivation.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The present socio-economic status of rural entrepreneur includes age group, family structure, gender, nature of business were analyzed and presented below:

Age of Rural Entrepreneurs

It was required to have an approach in to the age of rural entrepreneurs. The reason being the capabilities of a person in doing different jobs vary at different stages as the confidence level, stamina etc at a particular time will differ with the passage of time. The respondents were classified on the basis of their age at the time of survey to identify which age group had participated more energetically in rural entrepreneurial activities.

Table 1- Age of Rural Entrepreneurs

AGE GROUP	MANUFACTURING		SERVICE		TOTAL	
	in Nos	Percentage	in Nos	Percentage	in Nos	Percentage
20-30	43	22.05	13	13.98	56	19.44
31-40	75	38.46	43	46.24	118	40.97
41-50	57	29.23	28	30.11	85	29.51
Above 50	20	10.26	9	9.68	29	10.07
TOTAL	195	100	93	100	288	100

VALUE OF $\chi^2 = 7.11$

TABLE VALUE @ 0.05% LEVEL = 7.81

Table-1 depicts the present age of rural entrepreneurs surveyed in Jagatsinghpur district of Odisha. It was found that 41 percent of the rural entrepreneurs were in the age group of 31-40 years. 29.5 percent of the rural entrepreneurs were in the age group of 41-50 years. The percentage of rural entrepreneurs in the age group 20-30 was 19.4 percent and 10.1 percent in the age group of 50 years and above. Since the value of chi-square is 7.110 at degrees of freedom 3 is less than table value 7.81, it can be concluded that there is no relationship between age group and activities of the rural entrepreneurs.

Gender of Rural Entrepreneurs

Table-2 Gender of Rural Entrepreneurs

GENDER	MANUFACTURING		SERVICE		TOTAL	
	in Nos	Percentage	in Nos	Percentage	in Nos	Percentage
MALE	153	78.46	58	62.37	211	73.26
FEMALE	42	21.54	35	37.63	77	26.74
TOTAL	195	100	93	100	288	100

Gender of the respondents was collected to know the proportions of male and female entrepreneurs that participated in entrepreneurial activities in the above said districts. The data as shown in Table-2 represents that 73.3 percent of the rural entrepreneur were males, whereas 26.7 percent of the rural entrepreneurs were females. Besides, sector wise analysis represented that 78.5 percent of rural entrepreneurs in the manufacturing sector were males and 62.4 percent in service Sector.

Family Structure

One of the vital factors influencing the success of an entrepreneur is the support from his family that depends upon the structure of the family. The increase in desires, aspirations, ambitions, and outlook made the people to live independently and to achieve their own requirements. Another interesting factor is, whether the entrepreneurs belong to nuclear or joint family. The data has been collected and shown in Table-3 which represents that 69.1 percent of the rural entrepreneurs belonged to nuclear family structure and 30.9 percent belonged to joint families. The value of chi-square at 0.05 level was found to be insignificant. Hence, it shows that there is no connection between the family structure and type of the firm.

Table-3 Family Structure of Rural Entrepreneurs

TYPE	MANUFACTURING		SERVICE		TOTAL	
	in Nos	Percentage	in Nos	Percentage	in Nos	Percentage
JOINT	58	29.74	31	33.33	89	30.9
NUCLEAR	137	70.26	62	66.67	199	69.1
TOTAL	195	100	93	100	288	100

VALUE OF $\chi^2=0.38$

TABLE VALUE @ 0.05% level=5.99

Nature of Business Organization

The different forms of business organizations chosen by the respondents have been represented in Table-4. Sole proprietorship was preferred business organization in the said districts and 87.8 percent of the respondents opted for it, whereas partnership constituted 12.8 percent. The types of organizations set up for micro and small enterprises (MSE) were generally proprietary and few were partnership.

Table-4 Nature of Business Organization

NATURE	MANUFACTURING		SERVICE		TOTAL	
	in Nos	Percentage	in Nos	Percentage	in Nos	Percentage
SOLE-PROPRIETOR	170	87.18	83	89.25	253	87.85
PARTNERSHIP	25	12.82	10	10.75	35	12.15
TOTAL	195	100	93	100	288	100

CONCLUSION

The analysis of socio-economic factors reveals that the process of formation of entrepreneurship in rural areas is not restricted to any particular age group or gender. It is found that a high percent of rural entrepreneurs had taken up the initiative to start enterprise in the age group of 31-40 years. The fondness towards entrepreneurship in the middle age group is more primarily because no other substitute career option is available once they cross this age. 73.3 percent of the rural entrepreneurs were males, whereas 26.7 percent of the rural entrepreneurs were females. Sole proprietorship was the most chosen form of business organization as 87.8 percent of the rural entrepreneurs opted for it. Entrepreneurs belonging to joint family though fewer in numbers earns equally with that of nuclear family. So, it can be said that Joint family is equally skilled with nuclear family in respect to earnings. Female entrepreneurs though fewer in numbers were also equally capable with male entrepreneurs in regard to earnings. It reveals that financial soundness of the rural entrepreneurs is believed to inspire the growth of entrepreneurship.

Though partnership organizations are less in number still they are also earnings with proprietorship form of business. The overall analysis of these variables shows that socio-economic conditions of the rural surveyed entrepreneurs in the district is more than average and this is a sign of good foundation of entrepreneurs with a high outlook of growth. Hence, on the basis of the above findings, it can be concluded that the hypothesis set for the above analysis that socio-economic factors are not encouraging towards the growth of rural entrepreneurship, could not be accepted.

Rural entrepreneurship is the way of converting the developing country into developed one. Also rural entrepreneurship is the solution to removal of rural poverty in India. Therefore, there should be more steps taken towards integrated rural development programs. There should also be efficient regulated market and government of India should also lend its helping hand.

REFERENCES

- 1-Anjali Ghosh, (2011), Predicting Entrepreneurial Success: A Socio-Psychological Study, the Journal of Entrepreneurship, No.11 (1), January-June 2011.
- 2-Barua A Nissar and Mali Archana (2011), "Entrepreneurship and Its Role in the Growth of Micro and Small Enterprises: A Case Study of West Bengal", Small Enterprise Development, Management & Extension Journal, Vol. 38, No. 2, pp. 69-83.
- 3-Desai Vasant (2010), "Entrepreneurship and small business management", Himalaya Publishing House, New Delhi, 2004.
- 4-Geetha and Govindappa (2011), "Socio-economic background and problems of entrepreneurs in Industrial estate: A case study of Industrial Estate in Davangere, SEDME, and vol. 38. No. 3. september, pp 1-41.
- 5-Kondaiah C., (1990), "Entrepreneur Development in Rural Areas", SEDME, Vol. XVII, March 1990. Krejcie and Morgan's formula of "Determining Sample Size for Research Activities". Available at <http://people.usd.edu/~mbaron/edad810/Krejcie.pdf> (accessed on 20th June, 2012).
- 6-KumarJyoti and Lalhunthara (2012). "Socio-economic background of micro Entrepreneurs in Aizawal District, Mizoram." SEDME, vol. 39. No. 2. June, pp-1-17.
- 7-Malkappa Ambala and Laxman Rajnalkar (2011), "Implementation and Impact of PMEGP scheme in Hyderabad Karnataka Region: A study, SEDME, vol. 38, no. 2. June, pp 53- 67.
- 8-Nath Dwaraka H.D. (2013). "Strategies for employment generation in Rural India- a critical evaluation." kurukshetra, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 27-31.
- 9-Pal, Satya (2013). Rural entrepreneurship in India: Challenges and problems, *TMIMT International Journal*, vol.4 issue 4.
- 10-Babu, V. (2012). Challenges and prospectus of successful women entrepreneurs-A case study in Davangere City, *International Journal of research in commerce, economics and Management*
- 11-Singh J, S.G., (2013). Fostering Rural Entrepreneurship in India, retrieved from <https://sdmimd.ac.in/rubanomics/articles/FosteringRuralEntrepreneurship>
- 12-Ghosh, Sudipta (2013). Entrepreneurship: An overview of the issues and challenges in the context of rural development in India, *Business Spectrum*, vol.1, no.1
- 13-Venkateswarlu, P. & Ravindra, P.S. (2015). An empirical Study on Problem and Prospects of Rural Entrepreneurs with Special reference to Visakhapatnam District. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, vol.2 issue 2.
- 14-Problems and prospects of rural entrepreneurship in India- a study on rural tourism in India by Ravikumara B.M from <http://itirj.naspublishers.com/?p=99>
- 15- <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/economics/opportunities-and-challenges-for-rural-entrepreneurship-in-india-economics-essay.php> <http://www.preservearticles.com/business/major-problems-faced-by-rural-industries>